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Effectiveness of the Implementation of the Tourism Code on the Primary Tourism Industry in the Municipality of Basud, Camarines Norte

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I. Abstract

This study determined the effects of the implementation of the Tourism Code on the primary tourism industry in the Municipality of Basud, Camarines Norte. Specifically, it aimed to determine: (1) the profile of primary tourism industries in terms of annual income, tourist arrivals, number of employees, land area, and initial capital; (2) the level of effectiveness of the Tourism Code in terms of environmental protection, climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction integration, gender and development integration, scenic views and cultural preservation, accreditation, tourist influx and arrival reports, licensing regulation, and halal seal encouragement; (3) the challenges encountered by tourism industries in implementing the Tourism Code; and (4) the relationship between the profile of tourism industries and the effectiveness of Tourism Code implementation.

The study utilized a descriptive research design using a survey questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument. The respondents were owners and representatives of primary tourism industries in Basud, Camarines Norte. Data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, rankings, weighted means, and Somers' Delta.

The findings revealed that most tourism establishments were small-scale enterprises, with the majority having annual incomes below Php100,000, tourist arrivals ranging from 500-1,000 annually, land areas below 500 square meters, and limited employees. These findings indicate differences in operational capacity among tourism industries.

The implementation of the Tourism Code was generally assessed as Effective. Environmental Protection obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.17, Accreditation 3.10, and Licensing Regulation 3.14, all interpreted as Effective. Tourist Influx and Arrival Reports received the highest assessment among the indicators, while Halal Seal

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Encouragement obtained the lowest weighted mean but remained within the Effective category.

The major challenges identified by tourism industries included the high cost of environmental compliance, which ranked first among the concerns, followed by difficulties related to accreditation requirements, documentation procedures, and limited technical assistance. These challenges indicate that while tourism establishments recognize the importance of compliance, financial and administrative limitations affect the full implementation of some Tourism Code provisions.

Results also showed that most tourism profile variables had no significant relationship with the effectiveness of Tourism Code implementation, suggesting that the implementation of the Tourism Code was generally consistent regardless of the characteristics of tourism industries. However, annual income showed a significant inverse relationship with Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Reduction Integration, indicating that income level may influence participation in climate resilience practices.

The study concluded that the Tourism Code of Basud serves as an effective framework for tourism governance, environmental protection, and sustainable tourism development. However, challenges related to financial limitations, compliance costs, and regulatory requirements remain barriers to achieving full implementation.

Based on the findings, it was recommended that the Municipal Government of Basud strengthen monitoring, orientation, and capacity-building programs to improve compliance with Tourism Code provisions. Support mechanisms addressing environmental compliance costs, accreditation requirements, and operational challenges should also be enhanced. Furthermore, stronger collaboration among tourism stakeholders should be promoted to sustain effective tourism policy implementation.

II. Keywords: *Tourism Code, Tourism Industry, Tourism Industries, Local Governance, Tourism Development, Environmental Compliance, Accreditation*